

HISTORY

THE CHANGES IN THE TERRITORY OF THE ROMANIAN DANUBE PRINCIPALITIES AND ROMANIA UNTIL THE PARIS PEACE TREATY OF 1947

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Abstract

This article aims to discuss the territorial evolution of Romania starting from the foundation of the two Danube Principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia in the 14th century through the period of the Ottoman vassalage and the formation of the kingdom in the mid-19th century until the time when the current state borders were defined in the Paris Peace Treaty after the Second World War.

Keywords: Romania, Moldavia, Wallachia, Danube Principalities, border changes, 20th century.

Definition of the Romanian state space

Although Romanian statehood has roots dating back to the Middle Ages, its independence is the result of changes in the 19th century – a feature that puts it in line with most states in the Balkan and Eastern Europe. However, its state space has perhaps undergone more changes in the last 500 years than that of its neighbours, Romanian statehood has had a specific historical development, which has often brought with it specific territorial changes over time.

The Romanian state space has been shaped by tangible historical and geographic factors which have had a fundamental impact on the process of change. One of the most important of these is the fact that the territory inhabited by the Romanian ethnic group has historically been a grey zone, an intermediate or collision zone between great powers. Byzantium, then the Ottoman Empire to the south, the Golden Horde, then the Russian Empire to the east, and to, initially the Kingdom of Hungary, then the Habsburg Empire and later the Austro-Hungarian Empire the west. In the case of Moldavia, Poland and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth were the local middle powers with a strong influence in the Middle and Early Modern period.

But an equally important factor was the geography of the Romanian state space – the fact that it was geographically divided into three different regions of Europe, with Moldavia in the Eastern European plain, Transylvania in Central Europe and the semi-Balkan region of Wallachia – which in practice predestined the political division that was central to the first six hundred years of Romanian statehood.

From the formation of the Romanian principalities to Ottoman vassalage

The beginnings of the Romanian state space become more obscure the further back we look into the past. On the one hand, because the state itself only came into being in its modern form in the 19th century, the two principalities can only be considered as 'legal predecessors', and on the other hand, the general uncertainties of early Romanian history do not allow us to speak of a Romanian state in relation to the Dacian state, which can be considered as its real predecessor.[1]

Until the middle of the 19th century, the Romanian territorial organisation consisted of two principalities

with similar structures, but separate, namely the Principality of Wallachia and the Principality of Moldavia. These two entities were not only geographically contiguous, but also similar in structure, so that it is possible to present the changes in the Romanian state space in the early period through their history in parallel.

Records from the 12th century already show that a Neo-Latin-speaking people was at least in a relative majority in the lowlands between the Danube and the Carpathians, where a large Tatar, Cuman and Slavic population also lived at that time.[2] The common language and the increasingly prominent territorial identity of the Orthodox Church organised the New Latin-speaking ethnic groups into several loosely connected voivodeships, but the strength of Hungarian influence meant that for a long time they were not able to form a serious state. The region of Oltenia, which belonged to the Kingdom of Hungary under the name of Banate of Severin (Szörényi Bánság in Hungarian), was for a long time excluded from the region of Wallachia, while the Golden Horde extended its influence to Muntenia in these centuries.[3]

The change came at the beginning of the 14th century, when Voivode Basarab – in opposition to the Hungarian King Charles I – united Oltenia and Muntenia, thus creating the Principality of Wallachia. In the case of Moldavia, although Hungarian influence was considerable throughout the Middle Ages, Polish dependence was the dominant factor; the foundations of statehood were laid by Prince Dragoş in 1346. Moldavia covers the area from the eastern foothills of the Carpathians to the Dniester River and the Black Sea. It reached its greatest extent during the reign of Stephen the Great (Ştefan cel Mare), when it even included the territory of Pocuţia – the region north of Bucovina. Thus, at its peak, the Principality covered well over 100,000 km² – geographically slightly larger than the 94,000 km² of Wallachia.

However, with the gradual loosening of Hungarian and Polish dependencies, a new power emerged in the region in the 14th and 15th centuries in the form of the Ottoman Empire. Following the conquest of neighbouring states such as Bulgaria and Serbia, the two Romanian principalities also became Ottoman dependent, although not in the same way as their neighbours, as

they were not fully integrated into the imperial structure: the territorial unity of Wallachia was preserved, but the princes became vassals of the sultan in the following centuries. Moldavia lost its maritime exit to the Ottomans, its princes also became vassals, but retained their relative independence, also due to their relatively great geographical distance from the Sublime Porte – a structure that persisted until the end of the 17th century, at the beginning of the Phanariot period.[4]

The case of Transylvania deserves special mention, since it probably became a Romanian-ethnic majority territory for most of the Middle Ages, but certainly by the early modern period, and the Grand Duchy of Transylvania, which became a separate entity from the Kingdom of Hungary as a result of the Ottoman conquests, functioned as an Ottoman vassal and functioned in Romanian memory and memory politics as an element of Romanian statehood similar to medieval Moldavia and Wallachia.[5]

From the Phanariot era to the proclamation of the kingdom

The 18th century also marked a turning point in the development of the balance of power, when the main change being that Russia became a serious rival of the Ottoman Empire, and the area where the two empires met became the territory of the Danube Principalities as the natural geographical border between the two great powers.

One of the basic mechanisms of Russian foreign policy in the 18th century was to accelerate and extend the expansion of its interests towards the Balkans. As a result, the Russo-Turkish wars resumed in the mid- to late-century. The main theatre of the war between 1768 and 1774 was the territory of the principalities, and after the signing of the Constantinople Convention one year after the concluding Peace of Küçük Kaynardži on the 21st July 1774, the Habsburg Empire annexed Bucovina – and the region remained in Austrian hands until 1918.

The Peace of Bucharest, which ended the Russo-Turkish War of 1806-1812, also had a lasting impact. This is the reason for the political fragmentation of Moldova as a geographical and historical area for more than 200 years. The Russian Empire annexed the eastern part of the territory between the Prut and Dnieper rivers – and from then on the name Bessarabia began to be used, although according to Romanian historian Neagu Djuvara it originally meant only the southernmost corner of the territory, today's Budjak.[6]

By the first third of the 19th century, two main goals had been articulated by the political elites in Bucharest and Iași, three main goals for the short, medium and long term. The first of these was the unification of the two principalities, the second was the achievement of full independence, and the third was the unification of all Romanian-inhabited territories within a single state.[7]

The weakening of the Ottoman Empire at the beginning of the century, both in domestic and foreign policy terms, was favourable. Well aware of the opportunity presented by the situation – and having seen other events in the Balkans, such as the Greek and Ser-

bian struggles for independence or the case of Montenegro – the Romanian political elite began to gravitate increasingly towards Russia.[8]

In fact, the Crimean War (1853-1856) provided the opportunity for the manifestation of Romanian ambitions. Amidst the focus of the great powers in Eastern Europe, the rallies organised by the Romanians were effective, with several expressions of unification. France also played an important role, acting as a patron of the principalities and securing the return of the southern part of Bessarabia to Moldavia with a narrow Black Sea exit.

In line with the aforementioned Western interests, in 1858 Alexandru Ioan Cuza[9] was elected prince, first in Moldavia and then in Wallachia, which was the precursor to the unification that took place on the 5th February 1859 – or the 24th January according to the old calendar.[10] In 1861, the personal union of Moldavia and Wallachia was recognised by the Ottoman Porte, and the state, initially known as the United Principalities, became one of the medium-sized states of the region, with an area of approximately 123,000 km².

But diplomacy was not enough to achieve the next goal, the independence. The new Ottoman constitution of 1878 did not change the Romanian Principality's dependence on the Porte, and it became clear to the elite of Bucharest that war was the only way forward. Recognising this, Romanian troops became actively involved in the ongoing war of 1877-1878 on the Russian side, and at Plevna in Bulgaria, the barrel of a captured cannon was used to pour out the future royal crown, the Coroana de Oțel (Steel Crown).

The peace of San Stefano, which ended the war, guaranteed Romania's independence, and the Congress of Berlin confirmed it. Under this agreement, Romania ceded 3 counties of South Bessarabia – Bolgrad, Cahul and Ismail – to Russia, but in return received the central and northern part of Dobruja.[11] The country's territory thus increased to almost 138,000 km² and the form of government changed soon after. In March 1881, a kingdom was proclaimed; after the resignation of Prince Cuza in 1866, Charles of Hohenzollern-Sigmaringen, invited from the German Empire, became the first king of Romania under the name of Carol I.

The Second Balkan War and the Great Unification

The first territorial change in Romania in the 20th century was linked to the Second Balkan War, which the country ended up as one of the victors with territorial gains. The renewed war, which lasted from the 29th June to the 10th August 1913, was triggered by Bulgaria's territorial gains, which were considered unrealistic by its former Balkan allies. Romania joined in the 'second act' and on the 10th July declared war on Bulgaria, which was besieged on all sides and was forced to lay down its arms.

At the peace talks held in Bucharest in August, Romania took possession of the southern part of Dobruja – named Cadrilater[12] – an area of nearly 7,500 km², and thus the entire region. Although the Bulgarians and Turks were in absolute majority here, the new

acquisition with the town of Balchik gave a huge boost to Romanian national consciousness.[13]

The next territorial changes and the greatest in scale and impact is linked to the First World War. In August 1916, Romania, although a member of the Quadruple Alliance[14] and an ally of the Central Powers, entered the war on the side of the Entente Powers and launched an attack on Transylvania at the end of the summer. The result was a total failure; the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, with effective German help, repulsed the Romanian attack and then pushed on as far as Bucharest, occupying the city. From the Romanian side, by the beginning of 1918, virtually the whole of the Wallachian Lowlands had fallen, the Bucharest Peace Treaty was signed on the 8th May, and the Romanian king and government fled with the rest of the army to the former Moldavian capital, Iași. The border of Austria-Hungary was moved to the foreground of the Carpathians and a buffer zone was created while the coastal strip was jointly controlled by the central powers – Romanian statehood was limited to a part of Moldavia for more than half a year.

However, as the military defeat of the central powers became increasingly certain, Romanian decision-makers decided to go to war again at the end of November 1918 – this time with complete success. The first 'manoeuvre' concerned Bessarabia. On the 3rd March 1918, the new Bolshevik government of Russia concluded a special peace agreement with the Central Powers in Brest-Litovsk.[15] In this situation, the Romanian government saw the time as ripe to seize Bessarabia; in March 1918, Romanian troops attacked a Russia in a state of disintegration – on the 13th, the Romanian forces reached the Dniester River line. A puppet government was set up in Chișinău, which on the 9th April declared Bessarabia's accession to Romania 'for ever', a decision tacitly accepted by both the Entente and the Central Powers. By May 1918 Romania had thus lost its war against the Central Powers and concluded the harsh Bucharest Peace Treaty that sanctioned it. At the same time, however, with Bessarabia it had ceded a significant area of territory, roughly around 45,000 km², from Russia, which was descending into civil war.[16]

The seizure of Bucovina was similarly roundabout, and was made possible thanks to a favourable coincidence of the given situation, the main element of which was the inertia of the Ukrainian side. During the civil war in Russia, attempts were made in several regions of present-day Ukraine to organise an independent nation-state on the ruins of the tsarist regime, but none of these attempts was truly successful.

The Romanians living in the southern part of Bucovina convened a Romanian National Assembly in Czernowitz (Cernăuți) on the 27th October 1918, at which they declared the unification of Bucovina with Romania. The Romanian-Ukrainian territorial dispute after the withdrawal of the Austrian administration was finally settled by the entry of the Romanian army; the former border line was crossed in early November, Czernowitz was taken on the 11th November, and although the northern part of the region was controlled for a time by the Lviv-centred Western Ukrainian State, the

1919 Peace of Saint-Germain finally ceded the entire former Habsburg province to Romania.[17]

The acquisition of Transylvania was the greatest challenge in the great campaign to unify the new territories. On 3 November 1918, the Monarchy signed the armistice treaty at Villa Giusti near Padua, ending the war for the dual state.

However, it did not contain any concrete provisions for the Kingdom of Hungary, apart from the secession of Croatia-Slavonia, so one of the first tasks of the government of Mihály Károlyi, who came to power on the 31st October in the heat of the Autumn Revolution, was to conclude an independent treaty.[18] For Hungary, which would become independent a few days later, this took the form of a second 'round', the Belgrade Military Convention, signed on the 13th November.[19] This marked (on paper) the end of the Great War. However, there was another factor; the time, which also did not favour the Hungarian side, as French General Franchet d'Espèrey, the leader of the Entente forces in the Balkans, reached the Sava – the historic border between Hungary and Croatia – by early November, and the Czechoslovak Army invaded Upper Hungary on the very day the document was signed.

The Romanians also broke the terms of the Belgrade Convention and invaded Transylvania, declaring war on Hungary. The Romanian National Council was established in Budapest on the 31st October and moved from there to Arad, where it worked with the effective help of the local Romanian national councils to gradually take political power over Transylvania. At this point the 'ethnic question' could not even be resolved by a more democratic, federal reorganisation. The leaders of the Transylvanian Romanians, already aware of the Entente's position on historical Hungary, were in full agreement in demanding union with Romania. The first manifestation of this will came on the 1st December 1918 when the Transylvanian Romanian delegates of Romanian assemblies voted for the unification of Transylvania with Romania in Alba Iulia.

The renewed Romanian entry into the war resulted in the almost total crushing of Hungary. The Romanian Royal Army first advanced as far as the demarcation lines marked by the Entente, then took Budapest in August 1919 and by the end of the summer it was close to the Austrian border.

After the First World War, the final Romanian borders in Transylvania were fixed by the Treaty of Trianon, signed on the 4th June 1920, under which the Kingdom of Romania acquired Transylvania, Partium,[20] the southern part of Maramureș[21] and, after a 'duel' with Serbia, the eastern one-third of Banat[22] from Hungary. Romania's territory increased from 137,903 km² at the beginning of the war to 295,049 km², making it a regional centre power and the largest territorial extension of its history.

The changes of World War II and the borders of the modern Romanian state

In the interwar period, there were no border changes that affected Romania in any way – it was the second year of World War II that brought the first change.

In the summer of 1940, there was palpable tension between Hungarian and Romanian diplomacy, with both countries deploying hundreds of thousands of troops along their common border in July and the outbreak of another war was on the brink. The tense situation was finally 'resolved' by the Axis powers' settlement with the Second Vienna Award on the 30th August 1940. Negotiations, under German and Italian arbitration, settled the territorial dispute by awarding 43,104 km² of Northern Transylvania to Hungary.

That year, Romania suffered further territorial losses under German pressure. On the one hand, it had to cede Bessarabia to the Soviet Union, and on the other, in the south, South Dobruja – the region acquired during the Second Balkan War – to Bulgaria. These decisions were recognised by the victorious powers as valid after the end of the world war.

The following year, after the German invasion of the Soviet Union, Romania received compensation for the occupied Ukrainian territories; it took over the former Ottoman territory of Yedistan, east of the Dniester, which included the city of Odessa.[23] This was a short-lived acquisition, however, and in 1944, Soviet troops advancing westwards retook the area.

Under the Paris Peace Treaty, signed on the 10th February 1947, which formally ended the war, Romania lost the Bessarabian territories and did not regain the Cadrilater, North Bucovina nor Bessarabia, but the territorial integrity of Transylvania was restored by the annulment of the Second Vienna Award.

Since then, apart from the exchange of a few islands in the Danube Delta,[24] there has been no territorial change in the Romanian state space, therefore Romania has now been covering an area of 238,397 km² for more than 78 years, and most probably there are no signs of change in the near future – unless pro-unification opinions and movements start to gain strength in the Republic of Moldova.[25]

Conclusion

To sum up, today's Romania is several times larger in area than the first medieval principalities, and roughly twice as large as the Kingdom of Romania at its foundation in 1861.

The twentieth century was a period in which the country owed almost all of its territorial acquisitions, but also their retention, mainly to its successful participation in the wars of the age – the Second Balkan War, the First World War – and to its prudent political responses in those situations, such as the evasion during the last phase of the Second World War.

Changes in the territory of Romania in the 18th-20th centuries.

Source: <http://terkeptar.transindex.ro/belso.php?nev=3>.

References

1. Djuvara, Neagu: A Brief Illustrated History of Romanians. Humanitas, Bucharest, 2021.
2. Djuvara, 2021.44-64.
3. Oltenia is the region on the Western side of Wallachia, while the region of Muntenia covers the Central and Eastern parts of the principality. In detail: Djuvara, 2021. 77-86.

4. Phanariots (in Romanian: Fanarioți) were members of prominent families of Greek origin from the main Greek quarter of Phanar of Istanbul, who occupied important positions in the Ottoman Empire and were regularly appointed princes of Moldavia and Wallachia during the 18th and 19th centuries – marking the Phanariote period in Romanian history.

5. Boia, Lucian: Cum s-a românizat România. Humanitas, Bucharest, 2024. 20-42.
6. Budjak is a historical region that was part of Bessarabia from 1812 to 1940. Situated along the Black Sea, between the Danube and Dniester rivers, this multi-ethnic region covers an area of 13,188 km². Djuvara's idea about the etymology of the word 'Bessarabia' in detail: Djuvara, 2021. 78-79.
7. Csüllög, Gábor – Gulyás, László: A román állam területi kialakulásának története I. A. Középkortól a Román Királyság kikiáltásáig 1881). Közép-Európai Közlemények, 2012. 5. évf. 3-4., 122.
8. Djuvara, 2021. 272-274.
9. Alexandru Ioan Cuza (1820-1873) was the first domnitor (prince) of the United Principalities through his double election as Prince of Moldavia on the 5 th January 1859 and Prince of Wallachia on the 24 th January 1859, which resulted in the unification of the two states.
10. Raffay, Ernő: A Vajdaságtól a birodalomig. Az újkori Románia története. JATE Kiadó, Szeged, 1989. 19-26.
11. Dobruja – or Dobrogea in Romanian – is the coastal region of Romania by the Black Sea, and by that name we normally mean the central- and northern parts of the whole that are parts of Romania today with an area of 15,588km².
12. Cadrilater or Southern Dobruja – today part of Bulgaria – covering an area of 7,412 km² was part of since the Treaty of Bucharest in 1913 until the Treaty of Craiova in 1940.
13. Djuvara, 2021. 306-309.
14. Quadruple Alliance was a defensive military alliance between Germany, Austria-Hungary Italy and Romania from the 18 th October 1883 – when the Kingdom of Romania joined the Triple Alliance of 1882 – until its expiration in 1915. Until the end of the war, only King Carol I and a handful of senior Romanian politicians knew about the signature of the contract.
15. The Treaty of Brest-Litovsk was a separate peace treaty signed on the 3rd March 1918 between Soviet Russia and the Central Powers, by which Russia withdrew from World War I. The treaty was signed at Brest-Litovsk, which is now Brest, Belarus.
16. The Treaty of Bucharest was signed on the 7th May 1918 between Romania and the Central Powers following the stalemate reached after the alliance's victorious campaign of 1917.
17. Djuvara, 2021. 325-327.
18. The Aster Revolution or Chrysanthemum Revolution (Hungarian: Őszirózsás forradalom) lasted between the 28 th until the 30 th October 1918, led by Count Mihály Károlyi. The supporters of him, many of whom were demobilised soldiers, adopted the aster as the symbol of the revolution. In detail about the topic: Ormos, Mária: From Padua to the Trianon, 1918-1920. Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest, 1990.
19. The Belgrade Military Convention or the Armistice of Belgrade was an agreement on the termination of World War I hostilities between the Entente and the Kingdom of Hungary concluded in Belgrade on the 13 th November 1918.
20. Partium (from Latin word partium, the genitive plural of pars = part, portion) was a historical and geographical region in the Kingdom of Hungary during the early modern and modern periods. It consisted of the eastern and northeastern parts of Hungary proper.
21. Maramureş is a geographical and cultural region in today's northern Romania and western Ukraine, situated in the northeastern Carpathians along the upper Tisza River drainage basin.
22. Banat (in Hungarian: Bánság) is a geographical and historical region located in the southeastern part of the Pannonian Basin, today divided by Serbia, Romania and Hungary.
23. Yedistan is the region between the river Dniester and Dnieper bordering the Black Sea on the south-east.
24. The Danube Delta island changes took place in the form of two treaties signed by Romania and Ukraine in 1997 and 2003 fixing the border between the two countries along the river.
25. Current opinion polls on unification of the two countries in the Republic of Moldova show that in April 2025 32% were in favour, 58% apposed it, while in Romania the numbers were 33% in favour and 50% in opposition. Sources: <https://voceabasarabiei.md/sondaj-ue-sau-unirea-cu-romania-ce-ar-vota-moldovenii/> and <https://www.g4media.ro/sondaj-ce-cred-romanii-despre-unirea-cu-republica-moldova-ce-parere-aud despre-maia-sandu-si-ce-spun-despre-eventuala-invazie-a-rusiei-ar-trebuie-sa-ajute-romania-militar-statul-moldoveean.html>.